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Incongruence between Real and Ideal Selves Among Students in Relation to Perceived Parental Behaviour and Insecurity

*Dr. Dinesh Kumar**

The present study intends to examine incongruence between real and ideal selves among students in relation to perceived parental behaviour and insecurity. For the purpose, Parent-Child Inventory, Security Insecurity Test and Self-concept Inventory with different instructions were administered to a sample of 100 colleges students. Correlations and z-ratios were computed to analyse the data. The two selves were positively associated ($r = 0.49$; $p < .01$). Means of ideal selves were significantly higher than means of real selves in all cases. High self concept group had lower incongruity mean (2.88) than the low SC group (10.04) but quite contrarily high group (4.10). The favourably of parental perception showed insignificant correlation ($r = .09$) with incongruity although it was correlated positively with both the selves. Insecurity showed negative correlation with both the selves as well as with favourable perception of parents but it has significant positive correlation with incongruity ($r = .042$; $p < .01$). With regard to sex-difference, female group was higher on means of incongruity, insecurity and on parental perception but their self-concept means were lower than that of males. Both groups were identical on ideal concept means.

Introduction

Of the aspect of a man's experience, perhaps the most fascinating and real is that of the self. Self concept consists of whatever the individual views as belonging to himself. It contains the experience of his own body, his possessions, his family, his motive structure, drive states, defences etc. (Dana, 1966). William James (1890), One of the earliest American psychologists to have written extensively on the self, made a distinction between the self as a knower and the self as an object of the person's own knowledge and evaluation. Since then, the term self concept has come into use to refer to the second meaning (English & English, 1958; Symonds, 1951). Secord (1968, p. 349) indicated that in much theorizing, the self was referred to as a coherent, organized set of cognitions and feelings about one's person and behaviour as an object. In reviewing the self-concept Wylie (1968, p. 739) stated that many self-referent constructs relate to some of the person's own physical characteristics, thoughts, feelings and behaviour. After reviewing many definitions Wylie concluded that the self-concept includes a person's evaluations as well as his cognition (p. 740). Gergen (1971) described the self as the system of concepts used by the person to define himself. A person's self image and ideal self image have been separately conceptualized and recognized by a number of psychologists. Ideal-self is the image we have of ourselves as we could be, ought to be, or would like to be. It is characteristics of a person to be somewhat unhappy with his actual self and hence desires to become different type which would be more satisfying and glorifying. Hence, there is bound to be some disparity between a person's real self-concept and his ideal for himself. This disparity has accordingly been called the incongruency between the two selves.

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Objectives

In the present study, an attempt has been made to examine the inter-relationship between (a) the real and the ideal self-concepts (b) the incongruity between real and ideal selves, (c) favourably of the perception of parental behaviours and (d) feeling of insecurity. The ideal and real selves have not been studied in context with the college students of Patna, Bihar. This justifies undertaking of the present study.

Method of Study

Sample

Altogether 100 students (50 males and 50 females) of Patna University, Faculty of Arts, were included in the sample. The sample was incidental cum-purposeful one. In other respects the sample was matched so far as practicable.

Tools Used

(a) Mohsin self-concept inventory consisting of 48 Yes/No type items was used for measuring 'real' and 'ideal' selves. The statements were the same in both the forms but the instructions were different. For measuring real self-concept, a subject was required to judge whether the statements were applicable to him/her; and for measuring the ideal-self concept he/she was asked to judge whether the statements were true in judging him / her ideal person.

(b) Mohsin Parent Child Inventory, consisting of 50 items was used for measuring perception of parental behaviour. The subject was required to respond in terms of four categories ranging from 'perfectly true' to 'perfectly false'. Higher score indicated positive perception of parental behaviour and vice-versa.

(c) Mohsin Security / Insecurity Test consisting of 60 items was used to measure security and insecurity of the respondents. Each item had 3 possible responses 'Yes' 'No' and 'Undecided'.

Results and Discussion

Data consisted of five sets of scores : (a) Real self score, (b) Ideal self scores (c) Incongruity score (difference between real & ideal self scores), (d) Parental perception scores and (e) Insecurity scores. The data were analysed in terms of (i) relation between different set of scores and (ii) sex-difference.

Table - 01

Difference between real self-concept and ideal self-concept scores (N = 100).

Group	Real	Self-concept	Ideal	Self-concept	Difference	Z-ratio	Level of Significance
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Males	37.14	5.54	41.09	6.94	3.95	3.03	<.01
Females	32.49	9.10	40.64	5.79	8.15	5.29	<.01
Total	35.32	7.66	41.34	5.96	6.02	6.00	<.01

The results show that ideal self-concept means were significantly higher than real self-concept means in both the male and female subjects and also in the group as a whole. Thus, it appears that the individual's concept as ideal person is always higher than his concept of himself.

Table - 02

Means of Incongruity Score of the 'Above Mean' and 'Below Mean' groups of subjects (N = 100).

Tests	High scoring group	Low scoring group
Self-concept	2.88	10.04
Ideal-concept	7.24	4.10

Incongruity score means of the high and low scoring group (selected on the basis of the self-concept scores mean) differed largely in favour of the high scoring group. But, when groups were selected on the basis of the ideal concept score mean, the incongruity mean of the high scoring group was higher than the mean of the low scoring group.

Table - 03

Pearson's Product moment correlations between different sets of score (N = 100).

Variables	Self-concept	Ideal-concept	Incongruity	Perception of parental behaviour	Insecurity
Self-concept	0.49**				
Incongruity	-0.62**	0.19			
Perception of parental	0.38**	0.69*	0.09		
Insecurity	-0.71	-0.21	0.42*	- 0.45	

Note : ** denotes significance above .01 level.

A highly significant and positive correlation ($r = 0.49$, $p < .01$) between the self scores and ideal self scores showed that those who had a high concept of themselves and also a high concept of an ideal person. This is supported by Friendman (1955) who holds that normal shows a positive correlation of reported self-image and ideal self-image. Similarly Stagner (1964) found negative correlation between self-image and ideal self-image. Similarly Stagner (1964) found negative correlation between self-image and ideal self image in persons showing emotional maladjustment. From a highly significant negative correlation ($r = -0.62$; $p < .01$) between the self-concept scores and incongruity scores, it can be inferred that persons, having higher self-image have more realistic and less inflated concept of an ideal person, resulting in less incongruency between the two self. Contrary to this, ideal-concept scores had positive correlation ($r = 0.19$ $p > .05$) with incongruity scores.

Though, the favourably of perception of parents was positively and significantly associated with both the self and the ideal concept scores, in the second case, the association was comparatively much stronger ($r = 0.69$; $p < .01$) than the first $r = 0.38$; $p < .01$). It fits well with the Freudian thinking that the super-ego is the source of man's idealism and it develop through internalization of parental prohibitions and values in the process of identification. Thus, children who perceive who perceive their parental behaviour as favourable and encouraging will have greater identification and hence greater internalization was well evident in the present study. Hutt and Gibby (1964) also stated "morality is learned, the first instance, through identification, and as the child identifies with each parent with their moral values and behaviours."

The self-concept was positively associated with parental perception ($r = 0.38$). This findings gets support from the views expressed by Sullivan (1947) that a person's self-concept is significantly related to the attitudes he believes his parents hold toward him, it appears to be less closely related to the attitudes that parents actually report holding. The correlation between self-concept and favourably of perception of parents obtained in this study was not doubt positive and significant, but it was quite low. This shows that favourable perception of parental behaviour is not always associated with high self-concept. We therefore infer that unfavourable treatment by the parents giving rise to low self-concept may not essentially result in unfavourable perception towards them. The child may develop a tendency to undervalue himself and to overvalue his parents.

Thinking that maladjusted persons have larger incongruity as well as less favourable attitude towards parents, the writer had expected a negative relation between incongruity and parental perception but the result showed a near zero correlation (0.09). A high significant negative correlation ($r = -0.71$; $p < .01$) between insecurity and self-concept agrees with Strangner's conclusion (1964) "There is a general tendency for person who feel insecure to evaluate themselves poorly. Between insecurity and ideal self-scores also the correlation was negative, but it was low ($r = -0.21$); $p < .05$). The result showed a positive and significant correlation ($r = 0.42$; $p < .01$) between insecurity and incongruity which agreed with the most widely noted position of Rogers and his co-workers (Rogers & Dymond 1954) that such a disparity is a general indicator of maladjustment. Thus, a positive and significant correlation between insecurity which is a symptom of maladjustment and incongruity which too is associated with maladjustment, was quite expected. The write obtained a highly significant negative correlation ($r = 0.45$; $p < .01$) between insecurity and favourable perception of parents which is quite reasonable.

Table-04

Means, Standard Deviations and Difference between the means of males & females.

Groups Scores	Male (N=50)		Female (N = 50)		t-ratio	Level of Significance
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Self-concept	37.14	5.54	32.49	5.19	4.34	<.01
Ideal-concept	41.08	6.94	40.55	5.79	0.41	NS
Incongruity	3.94	3.55	8.14	4.69	0.83	NS
Favourably of perception of parental behaviour	141.91	17.185	154.51	13.01	4.13	<.01
Insecurity	12.86	5.45	19.86	6.25	5.98	<.01

The results of table shows that the self-concept mean of females (32.49) was lower than that of males (37.14). Quite contrarily, Whiteside (1976) found both younger and older girls and better self image than the boys of the same age, a Wylie (1964) remarks we can't clearly state that women's self concept are always more favourable than are men's self-concept. Similarly, higher incongruity Mean in females disagrees with previous findings. Matteson (1955) and Turner & Vanderlippe (1958) hadn obtained no sex-difference in this regard but Perkins (1958) found higher congruence in girls. It is only in the case of ideal scores that the two means were almost equal. Hence, it appears that the ideal self of the two groups was affected by some common factors, i.e. the social and cultural environment. The r-result showed that female group had more favourable perception of parents as well as higher insecurity.

Table - 05

Correlation in the two groups and significance of difference between the correlation.

Test	Males (N=50)		Females (N=50)		Z-correlation	Level of Sig.
	r	Level of sig.	r	Level of sig.		
Self concept Vs Ideal concept	0.54	<.01	0.34	<.05	1.26	NS
Self-concept Vs	0.32	<.05	-0.75	<.01	3.31	<.01

Incongruity						
Ideal concept Vs Incongruity	0.21	N.S.	0.10	NS	0.74	N.S.
Self-concept Vs parental percep.	0.36	<.01	0.24	NS	0.69	N.S.
Ideal concept Vs parental percep.	0.27	<.05	0.83	<.01	4.64	<.01
Incongruity Vs parental percep.	0.06	N.S.	0.07	NS	0.11	N.S.
Self concept Vs Insecurity	-0.19	N.S.	-0.86	<.01	6.01	<.01
Ideal concept. Vs Insecurity	-0.21	N.S.	-0.13	NS	0.41	N.S.
Incongruity Vs Insecurity	0.27	<.01	0.39	<.01	0.21	N.S.
Insecurity Vs parent. Percep.	-0.63	<.01	-0.09	NS	3.46	<.01

A perusal of the correlation chart reveals a consistent relation for both the groups i.e., both the groups were characterized by a positive correlation between self and ideal, a negative relation between self and incongruity and insignificant relation between ideal and incongruity and so on. However it is essential to point it out that the two sex-groups were not matched on all pertinent factors, through they were selected from the same population of Patna University Arts students, and were similar with respect to age, education, socio-economic status etc.

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